

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: KENYA

Committing to Action for Freshwater Ecosystems and Biodiversity in the African Great Lakes

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Introduction

Freshwater ecosystems provide essential services to billions of people worldwide (Lynch *et al.*, 2023). Despite their limited spatial scope (less than 1% of the planet's surface), they host 10% of all species, including a third of all vertebrate species (Tickner *et al.*, 2020). According to the World Wildlife Fund for Nature's Living Planet Report, freshwater species populations have witnessed the greatest overall global decline (83%) over the past 50 years (WWF, 2022). The planet is in the midst of a biodiversity and climate crisis with one third of freshwater populations now threatened with extinction. This is particularly evident in the African Great Lakes (Fig. 1), renowned as "hotspots of biodiversity" (Salzburger *et al.*, 2014) providing essential ecosystem goods and services to over 90 million people (Tebbs *et al.*, 2022).

Scientists studying the African Great Lakes, particularly Lake Victoria, began to notice significant and concerning changes caused by a range of interlinked anthropogenic activities in the early 1900s (Njagi *et al.*, 2022). These interlinked multiple threats include rapid population growth, overfishing, increased land cultivation, harmful algal blooms, non-native invasive species, urban and industrial pollution, eutrophication and, more recently, a rapidly changing ecosystem and biodiversity loss (Plisnier *et al.*, 2022; Achieng *et al.*, 2023). Although these mounting threats are widely recognized and debated, actions to address them have been monumentally slow over the past decades.

In a recent opinion piece, we found out that Africa lags behind in many aspects of biodiversity studies due to biodiversity data deficiency and access (Achieng *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, insufficient financial

Fishermen preparing boats for fishing along the northern tip of Lake Turkana in Ethiopia. Photo by Kevin Obiero.

and technical capacity impedes sound policy formulation and implementation for conservation and management. Despite this, very few studies have focused on the interplay between biodiversity and ecosystem change. Additionally, the lack of skilled professionals is a major impediment to data acquisition and design for the execution of high-quality scientific studies in the region. As such, our goal is to ignite the discussion about monitoring biodiversity loss in rapidly changing ecosystems in Africa by emphasizing the need for biodiversity data-driven policy interventions and management implementation in Africa (Achieng *et al.*, 2023). Consequently, there is still much that can be done to help protect freshwater biodiversity, particularly, if people better understand the benefits these plants and animals provide.

Calls to Action

During the recent UN Water Conference—the first of its kind in nearly 50 years—I argued that we can tackle the plethora of issues threatening freshwater supplies and biodiversity if we are willing to work together across 'knowledge silos' and across geographical boundaries to achieve internationally agreed upon water related goals and targets (Obiero, 2023).

The research my team and I have conducting over the past few years has made calls for collective stewardship of these vital aquatic resources for present and future generations through collaboration, knowledge sharing, and harmonization of research and management as critical elements to enhance conservation efforts in the AGL (Obiero *et al.*, 2020; Plisnier *et al.*, 2022). We specifically outlined three potential approaches to realize a long-term, multi-lake harmonized monitoring strategy. In a nutshell, there is need for support from a wide community of researchers and managers, as well as political will and sufficient financial, human, and infrastructural resources and capacities for its implementation (Plisnier *et al.*, 2022).

Independent organizations such as the International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD) and African Center for Aquatic Research and Education (ACARE), through the African Great Lakes Advisory Group Network, have committed increasing efforts to achieve shared goals for healthy AGL ecosystems through collaborative actions, including: capacity building, standardized data collection protocols, accessible information and data, harmonized research priorities, strengthened networks, and inclusive community engagement strategies.

There is ample evidence that the African Great Lakes region has a strong foundation to sustain economic and population growth in the future and higher levels of prosperity. If decision makers in the African Great Lakes build on these strengths and propose actionable recommendations, working intentionally to foster the productivity and well-being of all riparian communities, the region will innovate and sustain greater prosperity in the future. We call on governments to ensure that the new global framework works for people and nature by prioritizing measures to safeguard freshwater biodiversity.

In February 2023, we hosted the Annual Meeting of the African Great Lakes Stakeholders Network Conference to harness new perspectives for sound research, policy, and management in the African Continent. Here are some of the proposed resolutions and proposed actions by the conference attendees to protect freshwater ecosystems in the AGLs. We committed to:

- 1. Build regional capacity for the African Great Lakes through collaborative courses for scientists, with emphasis on women and early career scientists. We will:**
 - Grow a successful African Women in Science program that fosters gender-balanced science presence and leadership in the AGL region by increasing the number of African women in aquatic science and management leadership positions.
 - o Reach 50-100 African women aquatic scientists through leadership and knowledge-exchange programs.
 - o Develop and grow an East African, scientific Education and Training program to improve field-based and higher education experiences and knowledge in freshwater sciences for long-term sustainability of the African Great Lakes.
 - o Hold collaborative courses for 100+ scientists annually to share knowledge across freshwater lakes.

2. Create long-term systems to monitor and improve the health of the African Great Lakes. We will:

- Create and facilitate an accessible and open platform that houses scientific information and data from, and for, the African Great Lakes.
- Develop a long-term monitoring program for the African Great Lakes to understand lake conditions and trends through standardized data collection protocols for information that is

used by scientific, decision-making, and local communities.

- o Develop, implement, and share harmonized water monitoring practices that are based on a standardized template, but tailored to specific countries and regions.
- o Create, implement, and share information and data related to socioeconomic and market surveys, frame surveys, catch assessment surveys and hydroacoustic studies to inform policy decisions.

Fig. 1 The biodiversity rich terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems connectivity in Africa (Achieng *et al.*, 2023).

- o Map geographic areas of research and engagement for the African Great Lakes
- 3. Harmonize research and management priorities for accelerated outcomes for the African Great Lakes. We will:**
- Share information across borders to inform policies and management related to lake, fishery, and community health.
 - Develop a lake wide management plan template that can be customized for different lakes, using successful strategies and technologies.
 - Develop shared research and strategies to solve issues related to: gender equality, climate change resiliency, algal blooms, biodiversity, plastics, aquaculture, and others.
- 4. Strengthen the African Great Lakes network through shared, cross-basin knowledge and action. We will:**
- Facilitate an African Great Lakes scientific network through active lake Advisory Groups to establish region-wide solutions for the African Great Lakes and their communities.
 - o Hold frequent virtual and in-person discussions and exchanges to share information across institutions, borders, and lakes.
 - o Implement projects across countries and lakes.
 - Develop inclusive engagement strategies with and for communities so they understand, support, and take action for healthy lakes and people.
 - o Develop and implement methods, including education and citizen science, that empower communities to engage in water and health issues.

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Sindo Beach along the shores of Lake Victoria, Kenya. Photo by Kevin Obiero